

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE INFLUENCE OF HEREDITARY FACTORS ON THE OCCURRENCE OF PROSTHETIC STOMATITIS

Zeynalov H.,

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant

Aliyev T.,

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant

Department of Pediatric Dentistry

Ashrafov D.

Department of Orthopedic Dentistry, Assistant

Azerbaijan Medical University,

Baku, Azerbaijan

ABSTRACT

Based on studying the condition of the hereditary apparatus in patients with partial defects of the dentition before prosthetics using removable denture structures, to establish diagnostic markers to identify a tendency to prosthetic stomatitis. To determine the hereditary tendency to prosthetic stomatitis, the following was carried out: a clinical and genealogical examination, dermatoglyphic and discriminant analysis, cytogenetic methods for studying peripheral blood lymphocytes and a cytological method for assessing the functional state of the genome based on indicators of interphase cells were used. peripheral blood locytes.

Keywords: denture stomatitis, prognosis, diagnosis, hereditary predisposition, dermatoglyphics of the functional state of the genome, chromosomes, chromosomal aberrations, removable denture designs.

The preparations were examined by light microscopy using the Metascan-2 optical-electronic complex. Results. $\pm 4.14\%$ of cases), dermatoglyphic indicators 12 in men and 8 in women, associations of acrocentric chromosomes with four and eight chromosomes, frequency of acrocentric chromosomes (14th, 22nd) in associations 14th – 22.96th – 17.27%, frequency of chromosomal aberrations $4.98 \pm 0.32\%$, aberration spectrum of 1.27 breaks, 1.35 paired fragments; marker of allergic prosthetic stomatitis – gaps in the fifth chromosome; in neutrophil granulocytes of peripheral blood - a decrease in the chromatization index in men (less than 0.95 ± 0.03 conventional units) and sex chromatin in women (less than $21.58 \pm 1.83\%$), the appearance of pathological nuclei (more than $8.09 \pm 0.47\%$); positive correlations for all individuals between: nucleolar index and pathological nuclei; nucleolar index and micronuclei; chromatization index and sex chromatin. Conclusions. Prosthetic stomatitis is a multifactorial disease. The presence in patients with partial dentition defects anamnestic or de facto initial signs of periodontal tissue disease and a burdened allergic history is the basis for determining the susceptibility to prosthetic stomatitis, and the simultaneous identification of several genetic markers of prosthetic stomatitis. others should be taken into account in primary prosthetic patients when planning the manufacture of removable denture structures.

The combined effect of removable denture structures (RDD) on the prosthetic bed can cause various reactions of the oral mucosa (ORM) when using the denture, which vary from minor histological changes to clinical visible pathology - various types of dentures., 2]. It is known that PS is accompanied by pathological changes in the hereditary apparatus, which can be used in the diagnosis of this disease [3]. The search for ge-

netic markers that reflect the general state of the genome and its functional activity is an urgent problem in predictive medicine [4]. It is the neutrophil granulocytes of peripheral blood (NGCs) that are the cells of the internal environment of the body that reflect the general manifestations of the pathological process in the body [5] and can be markers of impaired implementation of hereditary information in PS. A simple, informative and accessible for the daily practical work of a doctor is a clinical and genealogical method for determining the hereditary predisposition to PS [6]. A more detailed probability of the occurrence of PS in patients with primary prosthetics is possible based on the assessment of hereditary predisposition based on the results of dermatoglyphic (DG) indicators [7]. The study of all four indices of the functional state of the genome (FSG) of somatic cells allows us to identify a holistic picture of metabolic disorders in PS [8, 9], and the identified relationships between the indicators of the interphase nuclei of the NGC in patients with partial defects of the dentition before prosthetics of the PCZ and patients with PS allow us to establish characteristic features inherent in individuals who are hereditarily susceptible and hereditarily not prone to PS, to find out the features of the formation of various types of PS and predict their course [10]. Therefore, it is advisable to focus on developing a set of criteria for hereditary predisposition to PS, which will allow us to identify a group of genetically burdened individuals. This approach to diagnosing PS at the preclinical stage will ensure the development of adequate warning signs. Based on a study of the state of the hereditary apparatus in patients with partial defects in the dentition, to establish prosthetics using removable denture structures to identify diagnostic markers to identify a tendency to PS. region, among which 134 patients with PS; 81 – patients aged 45–53

years with defects in the dentition before and after orthopedic treatment of STD to identify a tendency to PS and 45 clinically healthy individuals (45–50 years old) with intact dentition (control group). To determine the hereditary tendency to PS, a clinical and genealogical examination was carried out to identify historical data of a tendency to allergic diseases in members of each pedigree and the presence of periodontal tissue diseases. [eleven]. Three generations of each proband were analyzed, the total number of pedigree members was 1056 people. To create an objective model of the DG pattern of genetic burden of PS, a study of the DG pattern in 239 people was carried out, of which 117 patients with PS and 122 phenotypically healthy people. The assessment of the nature of DH signs was carried out according to the international classification. Of the 37 studied DG indicators with detailed information, 32 DG characteristics were selected. To develop a method for early diagnosis of PS [12], a discriminant analysis of DH indicators was carried out using the statistical data processing package STATISTICA [13]. Of these, 57 were patients with PS and 78 were healthy individuals (38 who had STDs and 40 people without STDs). The presence of AAC was assessed according to generally accepted criteria [18]. In addition to AAC, the frequency and spectrum of CA were studied in the obtained preparations [14] using the Metascan-2 optical-electronic complex. In total, 4612 associations in 5632 metaphases were studied. A cytological analysis of ORP epithelial cells was performed [15] in 63 patients before and after treatment for STDs and patients with PS. The control group consisted of 38 healthy individuals. To determine the degree of neutrophil chromatin condensation, 134 patients with PS and 81 people with dentition defects were examined before STD treatment. These patients were divided into two subgroups (55 people hereditarily predisposed to PS, and 26 people hereditarily not prone to PS) depending on the presence of PS in their pedigrees, periodontal tissue diseases and the results of microbiological, immunological, dermatoglyphic studies [16, 7, 12]. To establish changes in FSH in the epithelial cells of the ORP and NGC, an analysis was carried out using appropriate methods [17, 15]. The preparations were examined by light microscopy using the Metascan-2 optical-electronic complex, followed by assessment of their structural characteristics: chromatization index (IX), nuclear index (NI), pathological nuclei (PN), micronuclei (MN). In females, the indicator of the heteropyknotic X chromosome—sex chromatin (SH)—was calculated. An analysis of the correlation relationships between FSH of the interphase nuclei of the SORP and NGC was carried out within each group [15]. Thus, genetic predisposition to periodontitis was determined in 16.67±7.61% of men and 28±8.98% of women. Possible inheritance of allergic diseases was identified by pedigree in one woman (4±3.92%). The combination of obochnosological forms was registered in two pedigrees of men (8.33 ± 5.64%) and three pedigrees of women (12 ± 6.50%). The next part of the study was the study of the inheritance of periodontitis and allergic diseases in patients with various types of PS. Thus, during a clinical examination of 134 patients with PS of various origins, signs

of periodontal tissue disease were revealed in 128 (95.52±1.79%) and a burdened allergic history in 33 patients, which amounted to 24.63±3.72%. cases. Generalization of data established a genetic predisposition to periodontitis of patients with PS in 35.82±4.14% of cases, and among the pedigrees of men - 26.15±5.45% and women - 44.93±5.99% of cases, which is consistent with the results of previous studies [11]. Inheritance of allergic diseases amounted to 16.42±3.2% of cases, with 10.77±3.84% of men and 21.74±4.97% of women among pedigrees. Consequently, among women, a greater genetic burden of the formation of periodontitis and allergic diseases was determined compared with that of men, respectively, by 1.82 and 2.14 times. Considering that the genotype determines the formation of a pathological process as an etiological factor, and the formation of DH indicators is associated with the differentiation and morphogenesis of other organs and systems in embryonic development, analysis of DH characteristics can be used to assess genetic predisposition to various diseases, in particular to PS. Thus, in the group of men, 12 characteristics were identified, and in women, 8 characteristics (see table) that should be used to predict hereditary predisposition to APS. Constants were established to determine the hereditary tendency of diagnostic DH indicators of the right and left hands of patients: for men – 155.368; for women – 165.0079. A high degree of accuracy in determining the probability of PS of allergic origin has been proven: in the male sample in 89.17%, in women in 79.58% and in total in 84.37% [12]. The continuation of the scientific research was the determination of the characteristics of the chromosomal apparatus, which reflect violations of the immunogenetic status of the person being studied, genetic instability and hereditary predisposition to the disease. A study of 4612 associations in 5632 cells established that the association index, the number of associations and associated chromosomes in one cell prevailed in healthy people; in the case of PS, there were no significant gender differences. Between the above indicators both in normal conditions and in PS, positive strong ($r = 0.7$; $r > 0.7$ at $p < 0.05$) or moderate correlation ($r = 0.3$; $r > 0.3$ at $p < 0.05$). In peripheral blood lymphocytes stimulated by the mythen phythemagglutinin to proliferation, unequal amounts of AAX were determined. The average frequency of associations per cell was 0.98 versus 0.83 in the control, which is consistent with the results of previous studies [17]. In two cases, the APS was 1.5. At the same time, variability was noted in the number of associated groups of acrocentrics in the cell, as well as the number of acrocentric chromosomes in the association. %, the smallest – 15 (18.04%) and 22 (17.27%). In the case of PS, in contrast to the control, chromosomes 14 and 22 occupy an intermediate position in associative ability. At the same time, it has been proven that in individuals with APS, the D/G index (the ratio of associated chromosomes of groups D and G) and the average frequency of associations per cell increase significantly. An important fact is that the total number of associated chromosomes in a cell characterizes their associative ability more objectively than other indicators of associations [18]. It was found that in the

studied healthy people and patients with PS, the analyzed population of circulating lymphocytes consisted of seven classes. Normally, associations were most often observed with two and three chromosomes, and least often with seven chromosomes. AAX with eight chromosomes were observed in six-metaphase plates of different individuals. In patients with PS, a similar trend towards a decrease in the number of AAXs with an increase in the number of associated chromosomes has been recorded. At the same time, a significant increase in AAX with four (1.1 times) and eight (3.1 times) chromosomes was proven compared to the control ($p < 0.05$). The obtained quantitative characteristics of AAC were consistent with the results of the CA study. The group average frequency of the latter was significantly higher in patients with PS ($4.98 \pm 0.32\%$) compared to the norm ($2.84 \pm 0.21\%$). Changes in the spectrum of aberrations in the case of PS were revealed: an increase in the number of discontinuities by 1.27; and paired fragments by 1.35 times ($p < 0.05$). A marker of APS can be considered the presence of gaps in the fifth chromosome, an increase in the D/G index (the ratio of associated chromosomes of groups D and G) and the average frequency of associations per cell. An increase in the amount of AAX and CA indicates the presence of immunodeficiency, since it is precisely this that prevents the elimination of cells with a disturbed hereditary apparatus [19]. = 0.3; $r > 0.3$) correlations between cytogenetic indicators: associative index, the number of associations and associated chromosomes in one cell, the frequency of CA in normal conditions and in patients with PS ($p < 0.05$). In general, the features of the chromosomal apparatus have been established in healthy people and patients with PS reflect disturbances in the immunogenetic status of the individual under study, genetic instability and a tendency to PS. The most sensitive link in the implementation of biological information in the cell turned out to be RAI. and the hereditary apparatus in men, unlike women, more noticeable changes were found only in IX ($p < 0.05$) with a better level of despiralization of the X chromosome. The decrease in CV in patients after prosthetic prosthetics to $20.63 \pm 1.37\%$ ($p < 0.01$) may be due to the adaptation of the SORP to new operating conditions. In all cases, MN fluctuated within a wide range of the normal reaction rate from $1.13 \pm 0.26\%$ before prosthetics and $2.27 \pm 0.61\%$ in the case after prosthetic prosthetics. The fact of an increase in the frequency of PN in the case of prosthetic prosthetics, which differed from those in for people who did not need prosthetics, 1.34 times ($p < 0.01$). Even after prosthetics of the STD, the value of this indicator did not reach the norm. An integral indicator of the functional state of the body can be a combined study of cytological indices of NGC. At the same time, an increase in chromatin compaction was likely only in men who were hereditarily predisposed to PS ($p < 0.05$). in burdened and unburdened persons, the growth of PN was determined to be 2.28 and 2.35 times, respectively, compared to their normal number. However, only in women an increase in PV can serve as a biomarker of hereditary predisposition to PS. According to our data, the average value of CFS in healthy women ranges from 34.67 ± 2.17 to $24.98 \pm 5.19\%$. Its

most significant decrease was observed in women with dentition defects, especially with a hereditary tendency to PS. The next stage of the work was to study the features of the relationships between the karyogram indicators of genetically burdened and burdened PS. Positive relationships were established between AY and PU ($r = 0.41$ at $p = 0.003$), UA and MY ($r = 0.5$ at $p = 0.002$), IX and SC ($r = 0.27$ at $p = 0.002$) in genetically burdened and similar inverses between YaI and PN ($r = -0.01$ at $p = 0.08$), YaI and MY ($r = -0.08$ at $p = 0.001$), IX and SH ($r = -0.43$ at $p = 0.03$) in unburdened patients. A combined study of four NGC karyogram indices showed the dependence of the activity of biosynthetic processes on partial loss of teeth and sexual characteristics. patients, the advantage of disturbances in the structure of nuclear components and the decisive role of compaction of the X chromosome have been proven. In individuals with a genetically burdened history of PS, functional disorders of the regulation of cell metabolism came to the fore. Sexual characteristics of FSH in men burdened with PS include structural changes in the karyoplasm; in contrast, in women, functional disorders of coordination of the transition of euchromatin to heterochromatin, morphological changes in the nuclei and structural rearrangements of the chromosomal apparatus predominated. features inherent in those who are hereditarily prone to the occurrence of PS (see table). The use of established markers of PS will make it possible to timely identify the propensity for PS in individuals at the stage of planning the manufacture of CVD, in the stage of absence of clinical signs in the oral cavity, will allow us to determine the risk group among people who need prosthetics, carry out individual preventive treatment measures in a timely manner and prevent the occurrence of PS.

Conclusions

Prosthetic stomatitis is a multifactorial disease. The presence in patients with partial dentition defects, anamnestic or de facto, of initial signs of periodontal tissue disease and a burdened allergic anamnesis is the basis for determining the susceptibility to prosthetic stomatitis, and the simultaneous detection of several genetic markers of PS in such patients are early infected. which should be taken into account in primary prosthetic patients when planning the manufacture of removable denture structures. Prospects for further research in the future, it is planned to determine the role of hereditary factors in the severity of PS

References

1. Palijchuk I.V. Klinicheskie izmenenija sostojanija slizistoj obolochki rotovoj polosti, tkanej parodonta u bol'nyh kandidoznym i kombinirovannym proteznym stomatitom / I.V. Palijchuk, M.M. Rozhko, R.V. Kucik // Arhiv klinicheskoj mediciny. – 2011. – № 1 (17). – S. 79-81.
2. Palijchuk I.V. Sostojanie slizistoj obolochki rotovoj polosti, tkanej parodonta u bol'nyh allergicheskim i toksicheskim proteznym stomatitom / I.V. Palijchuk, M.M. Rozhko, R.V. Kucik // Galickij vrachebnyj vestnik. – 2011. – T. 18, № 1. – S. 73–75.
3. Palijchuk I.V. Opredelenie nasledstvennoj sklonnosti k proteznym stomatitom po pokazateljam

metafaznogo analiza / I.V. Palijchuk, L.E. Koval'chuk // Galickij vrachebnyj vestnik. – 2007. – T. 14, chislo

4. – S. 73–75.4. Genom cheloveka i geny predraspolzhenosti (Vvedenie v prediktivnuju medicinu) / V.S. Baranov, E.V. Baranova, T.E. Ivashenko, M.V. Aseev. – Sankt-Peter-burg: Intermedika, 2000. – 272 s.

5. Newburger P.E. Global analysis of neutrophil gene expression / Newburger P.E., Subrahmanyam Y.V., Weissman S.M. // *Cur. Opin. Haematol.* – 2000. – Vol. 7(1). – P. 16–20.

6. Palijchuk I.V. Opredelenie nasledstvennoj sklonnosti k proteznym stomatitam s pomoshh'ju kliniko-genealogicheskogo analiza i izuchenie funkcional'nogo sostojanija genomnejtrofil'nyh granulocitov perifericheskoy krovi / I.V. Palijchuk // *Arhiv klinicheskoy mediciny.* – 2010. – № 2 (16). – S. 54–57.

7. Palijchuk I.V. Razrabotka i obosnovanie ispol'zovanija prognozirovanija voznikovenija proteznyh stomatitov u pervichno protezirovannyh pacientov na osnove ocenki nasledstvennoj predraspolzhenosti po rezul'tatam dermatoglificheskikh pokazatelej / I.V. Palijchuk, L.E. Koval'chuk // *Sovremennaja stomatologija.* – 2010. – № 3 (52). – S. 155–160.

8. Palijchuk I.V. Izuchenie funkcional'nogo sostojanija genoma jepiteliocitov slizistoj obolochki polosti rta u bol'nyh raznymi formami proteznogo stomatita / I.V. Palijchuk, L.E. Koval'chuk, G.M. Erstenjuk // *Galickij vrachebnyj vestnik.* – 2007. – T. 14, № 1. – S. 61–65.

9. Palijchuk I.V. Citogeneticheskie pokazateli funkcional'nogo sostojanija genoma nejtrofil'nyh granulocitov perifericheskoy krovi u bol'nyh proteznymi stomatitami / I.V. Palijchuk, L.E. Koval'chuk, A.S. Jastrebova // *Vestnik stomatologii.* – 2010. – № 3. – S. 59–64.

10. Palijchuk I.V. Korreljacionnye svjazi mezhdru pokazateljami funkcional'nogo sostojanija genoma nejtrofil'nyh granulocitov perifericheskoy krovi u bol'nyh proteznoj stomati-ti / I.V. Palijchuk, L.E. Koval'chuk // *Ukrainskij stomatologicheskij al'manah.* – 2010. – №4. – S. 9–14.

11. Ornat G.S. Kliniko-laboratornaja ocenka imunologicheskikh i geneticheskikh faktorov techenija proteznyh stomatitov i obosnovanie medikamentoznoj korrekcii v kompleksnom lechenii: Avtoref. dis. ... kand. med. nauk: spec. 14.01.22 "Stomatologija" / Ornat G. S.; Ivano-Frankovskij Nacional'nyj medicinskij universitet. – Ivano-Frankovsk, 2002. – 20 s.

12. Pat. na poleznuju model' 44459, Ukraina, MPK A61V 10/00, A61S 13/00. Sposob doklinicheskoy diagnostiki proteznyh stomatitov allergicheskogo proishozhdenija u pervichno protezirovannyh bol'nyh / Palijchuk I.V., Koval'chuk L.E.; zajavitel' i patentoobladatel' Ivano-Frank. nac. med. un-t. – № u 200902350; zajavl. 16.03.09; opubl. 12.10.09, bjul. №19.

13. Statisticheskij analiz dannyh s paketom STATISTICA/T.I. Mamchich, A.Ja. Olenko, M.M. Osipchuk, V.G. Shportjuk. – Drogobych: «Vozrozhdenie», 2006. – 208 s.

14. Zerova-Ljubimova T.E. Citogeneticheskie metody issledovanija hromosom cheloveka (metodicheskie rekomendacii) / T.E. Zerova-Ljubimova, N.G. Gorovento. – M.: Vestn. centra nauchnoj informacii i patentno-licenzionnoj raboty, 2003. – 23 s.

15. Rats. predlozhenie 30/2319, Ivano-Frankovsk. Vyjavlenie DNK v citologicheskikh preparatah / Koval'chuk L.E., Koval'chuk N.V., Ilik V.V.; zajavitel' i patentoobladatel' Ivano-Frank. gos. med. un-t. – 1997